

Paper 2

A Conceptual Review on Technology and Its Impact on Work-Life Balance

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Abstract

Every organisation is concerned about the employee's satisfaction and productivity and work life balance is one factor which is contributing towards the achievement of job satisfaction and productivity. The change in work pattern has affected the employee's work- life post COVID-19. The technology has contributed tremendously for the smooth flow of work during this period. The technology is being used in every profession for the smooth flow of work. Work-life balance has become a significant feature of a healthy work environment. Work-life balance reflects an individual's positioning across career roles and non-career life roles as an inharmonious inter-role phenomenon. In the changeover to an information-based global economy, the lines between work and home are muddling as technology redesigns the work place and the nature of home life evolves. Imbalance happens when work life and home life directly battle with one another, due to toiling long hours and an inability to meet commitments at home, or to spending too much time at home, resulting in failure to complete responsibilities at work. Thus, achieving work-life balance involves finding a happy medium in which one can meet the responsibilities of both work and home. It is because of technology employees are able to connect with each other from different parts of the world and also have work-life balance during this COVID-19 era. This paper studies the ways in which adoption of technology impacts work-life of workers and strategies to improve work-life during this challenging period of COVID-19

Keywords: Work-Life Balance, Productivity, Technology, COVID-19. Job satisfaction.

INTRODUCTION

Balancing your professional and personal life can be challenging, but it's essential. Often, work takes precedence over everything else in our lives. Our desire to succeed professionally can push us to set aside our own well-being. Creating a harmonious work-life balance or work-life integration is critical, though, to improve not only our physical, emotional and mental well-being, but it's also important for our career. Work-life balance is the amount of prioritization an employee allocates between work and personal life. It is a process that enables both employers and employees to create a balance between professional life and individual life. A viable work-life balance urges a person to distribute one's time according to his/her priorities. However, the time for professional activities and personal matters cannot be equal. So, if an employee cannot develop an achievable work-life balance, you may be spending more time on

personal interests, which will negatively impact your job. With technology simplifying how and where we can access communications, a survey by CareerBuilder found that half of workers check their email outside of working hours. More worrying is the fact that 24 per cent of workers do so while engaged in activities with family and friends. Technology has a positive impact on work-life balance. It improves workplace efficiency. But since you're working from home due to the coronavirus effects, technology can help you create an in-office culture while you work from home and boost productivity. Technology helps you work smarter by connecting with your team across borders and collaborating on projects. It will positively impact your work, increase output, and boost revenue. Nevertheless, in some cases, technology can hinder your quality of life and the work you put out if misused. In attempting to address work-life balance, workers are generally trying to preserve both quality of life, and potential for career advancements, while employers are trying to preserve high productivity and reduce worker turnover and improve job satisfaction.

IMPACT OF TECHNOLOGY ON WORK-LIFE BALANCE

During the pandemic and lockdown period, the scenario at home was quite different from the normal scenario. All family members were confined within the house, no outdoor movement to socialise or for entertainment, and no support was available in household chores from the hired domestic helpers. During such an unprecedented scenario, most of the employed individuals had to focus on their professional demands, together with fulfilling their personal life needs. Anticipating the possibilities of economic slowdown, the fear of impending lay-off started penetrating in the minds of most of the employed individuals. Such thoughts made individuals put extra efforts to give their best toward their professional responsibilities to minimise the possibility of being laid-off and compromising on work-life balance at the same time. COVID-19 has altered what a good work-life balance looks like. Parents have to take care of their children as schools and day-cares have closed or moved online. Employees are now working from home, making it even more challenging to separate work life from home life.

Smart technology in the workplace has come on massively over the last number of years. The advancements have enabled employees to easily connect with global colleagues, work from virtually anywhere and created a whole new way of alert working. This new way of working has been heralded as the saviour for those who need a more flexible work schedule or for those whose commute takes its toll. But while many people say that tech-enabled remote working would give them a better work-life balance, a new survey has suggested this is not the case. Technology has positive as well as negative impact on work-life balance/Technology has a positive impact on work-life balance. It improves workplace efficiency. But since you're working from home due to the coronavirus effects, technology can help you create an in-office culture while you work from home and boost productivity. Technology has shaped the way we organize and maintain many different aspects of our personal and work lives. Individuals rely on technology to schedule appointments, store important documentation, run business operations, communicate with others, and keep in touch. With an overwhelming amount of new technologies emerging, the boundary between work and life is becoming blurred. Individuals

are able to stay connected virtually 24 hours of the day with both work and their personal lives through a variety of different mediums. Technology has a progressively substantial impact on how people organize their work, while others are increasingly relying on similar technologies to organize and manage their personal lives. Individuals have different perceptions of the depth and breadth of the boundaries between their personal and work lives, as well as different opinions as to whether or not the technology is seen as an intrusion into their life. While others disagree, some individual's welcome technology into their personal life, for work purposes, and view the convenience of the technology as an advantage to stay on top of work tasks when away from work. Devices encompassed by information and communication technologies (ICTs), such as phones, laptops, and tablets, have many additional functions such as playing games, streaming music and videos, and connecting with social media. Although these devices, and ICTs in particular, are a critical aspect in work organization and management, they are also a main source of entertainments for all types of audiences. ICTs serve multiple purposes by enabling contact with those outside of work such as family members and friends. Even though these technologies have created a new level of connection for family and friends, the breakthrough of this technology has substantially impacted the business world. Technology that gives employees the ability to work anywhere at any time also leaves them contactable by their employers anywhere at any time. Even if they are not strictly 'on call', there is a sense of urgency that comes with constant notifications and incoming emails. While the freedom to work more flexibly and even work from the comfort of your own home can give you a sense of control of your work-life balance, it can actually blur the lines between work and home life, making it difficult to switch your brain off. Additionally, when your working hours blend together with your home hours, employees can often ignore the fact that they haven't had a proper break from work. High achievers in particular can struggle with switching off and this can lead to overwork and burnout. With so many e-mails, there is information overload. It becomes difficult to be able to stay focussed and get certain tasks done. There is a lot more multi-tasking and altering of priorities. It is mentally exhausting when there is no break from the start of your day to the end. The intensity seems to progress throughout the day. It is not a relaxed environment.

Thus, several researchers have concluded that technology has its own merits as well as demerits for individuals.

STRATEGIES TO IMPROVE WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Accept that there is no 'perfect' work-life balance.

Don't strive for the perfect schedule; strive for a realistic one. Some days, you might focus more on work, while other days you might have more time and energy to pursue your hobbies or spend time with your loved ones. Balance is achieved over time, not each day.

Find a job that you love.

Although work is an expected societal norm, your career shouldn't be restraining. If you hate what you do, you aren't going to be happy, plain and simple. You don't need to love every aspect of your job, but it needs to be exciting enough that you don't dread getting out of bed every morning.

Prioritize your health.

Your overall physical, emotional and mental health should be your main concern. If you struggle with anxiety or depression and think therapy would benefit you, fit those sessions into your schedule, even if you have to leave work early or ditch your evening spin class. Overworking yourself prevents you from getting better, possibly causing you to take more days off in the future.

Don't be afraid to unplug.

Cutting ties with the outside world from time to time allows us to recover from weekly stress, and gives us space for other thoughts and ideas to emerge.

Take a vacation.

Whether your vacation consists of a one-day staycation or a two-week trip to Bali, it's important to take time off to physically and mentally recharge. Employees are often worried that taking time off will disrupt the workflow, and they will be met with a backlog of work when they return. This fear should not restrict you from taking a much-needed break.

Make time for yourself and your loved ones.

While your job is important, it shouldn't be your entire life. You were an individual before taking this position, and you should prioritize the activities or hobbies that make you happy.

Set boundaries and work hours.

Set boundaries for yourself and your colleagues, to avoid burnout. When you leave the office, avoid thinking about upcoming projects or answering company emails. Consider having a separate computer or phone for work, so you can shut it off when you clock out. If that isn't possible, use separate browsers, emails or filters for your work and personal platforms.

Set goals and priorities (and stick to them).

Pay attention to when you are most productive at work and block that time off for your most important work-related activities. Avoid checking your emails and phone every few minutes, as those are major time-wasting tasks that derail your attention and productivity. Structuring your day can increase productivity at work, which can result in more free time to relax outside of work.

The rise of the flexible workplace

Those who do maintain a successful balance between their often point to their flexible work schedules. Flexibility can pay off for employers in the long run.

Getting involved Leisure Activities

Leisure can be an effective coping strategy helping to maintain employee health and wellness. Leisure activities offer opportunities for recovery, rejuvenation and greater resilience in coping with stress.

Support from management

The culture and the environment of workplace and the extent to which the workplace provides support to help people deal with their family lives have a significant impact. All these factors, in turn, affect one's organizational commitment, and all the following variables influence work-life balance

Management also needs to help their employees in achieving work-life balance as many studies reveals that it increases the productivity, efficiency and minimizes labour turnover in organisation.

CONCLUSION

Work life balance is an integral for increasing productivity, efficiency and satisfaction. The management and employees have to take initiative to have work-life balance so that they are mentally and physically fit to perform their respective job. work-life balance is changing on a daily basis, and there is no universal formula on how to achieve a perfect balance between work and life. Rather, the work-life balance is focused more on how to achieve something in order to enjoy something. Work-life balance is all about providing employees with more flexibility when it comes to their working hours. it is important to have a positive work-life balance in order to enhance employees' productivity at work that would affect the well-being of an individual itself, the employer and the organization in general. Technology has provided more flexible work practices and the advancements have enabled employees to easily connect with global colleagues, work from virtually anywhere and created a whole new way of alert working. but it has also increased the speed at which information is shared and the expectation for responses, action and decision-making. Hours of work extend beyond the daily normal hours regardless of being able to adjust the hours within the 24-hour period, and therefore has generally been found to negatively impact on work-life balance.

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